

Horizon 2020

1. Data Summary

What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

Dataset Number of live-births in Vienna: Only to generate the new dataset (merged/processed data), which will then be used in the experiments.

Dataset Mean near surface temperature deviation: Only to generate the new dataset (merged/processed data), which will then be used in the experiments.

Dataset Merged/Processed data: The dataset will be used to perform means of visual datascience to find patterns between the mean near surface temperature deviation and the number of live-births in Vienna (available at DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.2648703).

What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?

Dataset Number of live-births in Vienna: It is a comma separated file to allow for easy reusability, which is additionally beneficial since it is an open and well established format.

Dataset Mean near surface temperature deviation: It is a tabular separated file to allow for easy reusability, which is additionally beneficial since it is an open and well established format.

Dataset Merged/Processed data: It is a comma separated file to allow for easy reusability, which is additionally beneficial since it is an open and well established format.

Will you re-use any existing data and how?

Dataset Number of live-births in Vienna: Re-used

Dataset Mean near surface temperature deviation: Re-used

Dataset Merged/Processed data: Created

What is the origin of the data?

Dataset Number of live-births in Vienna: The dataset was created by the city of Vienna.

Dataset Mean near surface temperature deviation: The dataset was published by the Eurostats (data source EEA).

Dataset Merged/Processed data:

What is the expected size of the data?

Dataset Number of live-births in Vienna: 38KB

Dataset Mean near surface temperature deviation: 2KB

Dataset Merged/Processed data: 1KB

To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Dataset Number of live-births in Vienna: The dataset could be reused by institutions (like universities), that are interested in the number of live-births in Vienna. One could e.g. try to correlate those with reasonable possible causes for the phenomena, that can be observed when visualizing the dataset.

Dataset Mean near surface temperature deviation: The dataset could be reused by any institution, who wants to analyze the climate change and its effects on society, economics and other areas.

Dataset Merged/Processed data: This dataset might be interesting for anyone, who is interested in finding patterns between the climate change and the number of live-births in Vienna. It could be extended in the future by new (more recent) data, to see if the same trends are still observable.

2. FAIR data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata, identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers)?

Dataset Number of live-births in Vienna: No

Dataset Mean near surface temperature deviation: No

Dataset Merged/Processed data: Yes Handle / DOI

What naming conventions do you follow?

Dataset Number of live-births in Vienna: Yes: The words in the name of the dataset are separated by using underscores “vie_201.csv”

Dataset Mean near surface temperature deviation: Yes: The words in the name of the dataset are separated by using underscores “cli_iad_td.tsv”

Dataset Merged/Processed data: Yes: The words in the name of the dataset are separated by capitalizing the first letter of each word “mergedData.csv”

Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

- mean near surface temperature deviation
- number of live-births in Vienna

Do you provide clear version numbers?

Dataset Number of live-births in Vienna: If the dataset is changed (updated to a new version with more recent measurements), then replacing the file with the new one (same name) and committing the changes with a commit message, explaining that the dataset was replaced by a new one, would be the strategy of choice to version the dataset.

Dataset Mean near surface temperature deviation: If the dataset is changed (updated to a new version with more recent measurements), then replacing the file with the new one (same name) and committing the changes with a commit message, explaining that the dataset was replaced by a new one, would be the strategy of choice to version the dataset.

Dataset Merged/Processed data: Changing the dataset generation (by adding columns or using another temperature deviation source) or updating the downloaded datasets (replacing them by more recent versions), would lead to a new dataset, that needs to be versioned. The new dataset would replace the old one (using the same name) and the commit message, would explain what changes were applied to the dataset.

What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

Dataset Number of live-births in Vienna:

- automatic: No metadata is collected automatically.
- semi-automatic: No metadata is collected semi-automatically.
- manual: No metadata is collected manually.

Dataset Mean near surface temperature deviation:

- automatic: No data is collected automatically.
- semi-automatic: No data is collected semi-automatically.
- manual: No data is collected manually.

Dataset Merged/Processed data:

- automatic: No metadata is collected automatically.

- semi-automatic: No metadata is collected semi-automatically.
- manual: Metadata is provided at documentation/description.txt (in the GitHub repository), explaining both the dataset and the result plots.

2.2. Making data openly accessible

Which data produced and/or used in the project will be made openly available as the default? If certain data sets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from voluntary restrictions.

Dataset Number of live-births in Vienna: Yes, externally for everyone

Dataset Mean near surface temperature deviation: Yes, externally for everyone

Dataset Merged/Processed data: Yes, externally for everyone

How will the data be made accessible (e.g. by deposition in a repository)?

Dataset Number of live-births in Vienna: Other: GitHub

Dataset Mean near surface temperature deviation: Other: GitHub

Dataset Merged/Processed data: Other: GitHub

What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Dataset Number of live-births in Vienna: Since the data is saved in the CSV format, any tool that can deal with CSV files can be used to work with the data (e.g. R, Python, Java, Excel etc.).

Dataset Mean near surface temperature deviation: Since the data is saved in the TSV format, any tool that can deal with TSV files can be used to work with the data (e.g. R, Python, Java, Excel etc.).

Dataset Merged/Processed data: Since the data is saved in the CSV format, any tool that can deal with CSV files can be used to work with the data (e.g. R, Python, Java, Excel etc.).

Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

Dataset Number of live-births in Vienna: NO

Dataset Mean near surface temperature deviation: NO

Dataset Merged/Processed data: NO

Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Dataset Number of live-births in Vienna: Yes, externally for everyone

Dataset Mean near surface temperature deviation: Yes, externally for everyone

Dataset Merged/Processed data: Yes, externally for everyone

Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited? Preference should be given to certified repositories which support open access where possible.

Dataset Number of live-births in Vienna: Other: GitHub (certified)

Dataset Mean near surface temperature deviation: Other: GitHub (certified)

Dataset Merged/Processed data: Other: GitHub (certified)

Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository?

Dataset Number of live-births in Vienna: Yes

Dataset Mean near surface temperature deviation: Yes

Dataset Merged/Processed data: Yes

Is there a need for a data access committee?

No

Are there well described conditions for access (i.e. a machine-readable license)?

Dataset Number of live-births in Vienna: There is no restriction on who can access the data, since it is provided on a public GitHub repository (and since it is licenced using the CC BY 4.0 licence). Furthermore the data is machine readable (due to CSV format).

Dataset Mean near surface temperature deviation: There is no restriction on who can access the data, since it is provided on a public GitHub repository (and since it is licenced using the CC BY 4.0 licence). Furthermore the data is machine readable (due to TSV format).

Dataset Merged/Processed data: There is no restriction on who can access the data, since it is provided on a public GitHub repository (and since it is licenced using the MIT licence). Furthermore the data is machine readable (due to CSV format).

How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

Dataset Number of live-births in Vienna: There is no need to ascertain the identity of the user accessing the data, as it is publically available.

Dataset Mean near surface temperature deviation: There is no need to ascertain the identity of the user accessing the data, as it is publically available.

Dataset Merged/Processed data: There is no need to ascertain the identity of the user accessing the data, as it is publically available.

2.3. Making data interoperable

Are the data produced in the project interoperable, that is allowing data exchange and re-use between researchers, institutions, organisations, countries, etc. (i.e. adhering to standards for formats, as much as possible compliant with available (open) software applications, and in particular facilitating re-combinations with different datasets from different origins)?

Dataset Number of live-births in Vienna:

- The dataset adheres to standardised formats: CSV
- The dataset is usable with available (open) software applications or software applications that are established and widely used in the respective community: Yes, it can be used e.g. with R, Python, etc.
- The dataset can easily be re-combined with different datasets from different origins: Yes, it was for instance recombined with the mean near surface temperature deviation dataset to create the merged/processed dataset.

Dataset Mean near surface temperature deviation:

- The dataset adheres to standardised formats: TSV
- The dataset is usable with available (open) software applications or software applications that are established and widely used in the respective community: Yes, it can be used e.g. with R, Python, etc.
- The dataset can easily be re-combined with different datasets from different origins: Yes, it was for instance recombined with the mean number of live-births in Vienna dataset to create the merged/processed dataset.

Dataset Merged/Processed data:

- The dataset adheres to standardised formats: CSV
- The dataset is usable with available (open) software applications or software applications that are established and widely used in the respective community: Yes, it can be used e.g. with R, Python, etc.
- The dataset can easily be re-combined with different datasets from different origins: Yes, this dataset is a combination of the two re-used datasets and can be combined with any dataset that has at least some values for the years from 2002-2017.

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?

Dataset Number of live-births in Vienna:

- No fixed system for the description is used

Dataset Mean near surface temperature deviation:

- No fixed system for the description is used

Dataset Merged/Processed data:

- A custom description system is used (please briefly outline and, if necessary, indicate where it is documented in more detail): the data and its content is described in the documentation/description.txt file

Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability?

The datatypes of the datasets are not specified (since they can be easily inferred by common statistic tools), thus no standard vocabulary is used.

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies?

Dataset Number of live-births in Vienna: No

Dataset Mean near surface temperature deviation: No

Dataset Merged/Processed data:

2.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?

Dataset Number of live-births in Vienna: Other: CC BY 4.0

Dataset Mean near surface temperature deviation: Other: CC BY 4.0

Dataset Merged/Processed data:

When will the data be made available for re-use? If an embargo is sought to give time to publish or seek patents, specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

Dataset Number of live-births in Vienna: March 4, 2018

Dataset Mean near surface temperature deviation: March 18, 2019

Dataset Merged/Processed data:

Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.

Dataset Number of live-births in Vienna: The dataset is usable by third parties.

Dataset Mean near surface temperature deviation: The dataset is usable by third parties.

Dataset Merged/Processed data:

How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

Dataset Number of live-births in Vienna: About 2 to 5 years, as it will get very outdated and presumably of only little interest to the public afterwards.

Dataset Mean near surface temperature deviation: About 2 to 5 years, as it will get very outdated and presumably of only little interest to the public afterwards.

Dataset Merged/Processed data: About 2 to 5 years, as it will get very outdated and presumably of only little interest to the public afterwards.

3. Allocation of resources

What are the costs for making data FAIR in your project?

Personnel: 0 PM

Other: 0 Euro

How will these be covered? Note that costs related to open access to research data are eligible as part of the Horizon 2020 grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions).

There will be no costs, as it will be preserved in the public GitHub repository, that allows to store projects that use less than 1GB of memory for free.

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Aleksandar Pavlovic (OCRID: 0000-0001-6887-9515)

Are the resources for long term preservation discussed (costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)?

Preservation decisions

- Aleksandar Pavlovic (OCRID: 0000-0001-6887-9515)

Costs

Personnel: 0 PM

Other: 0 Euro

4. Data security

What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)?

Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?

Dataset Number of live-births in Vienna: Other: GitHub (certified)

Dataset Mean near surface temperature deviation: Other: GitHub (certified)

Dataset Merged/Processed data: Other: GitHub (certified)

5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

Dataset Number of live-births in Vienna: No

Dataset Mean near surface temperature deviation: No

Dataset Merged/Processed data: No

Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

Dataset Number of live-births in Vienna:

- Personal data: No
- Informed consent:

Dataset Mean near surface temperature deviation:

- Personal data: No
- Informed consent:

Dataset Merged/Processed data:

- Personal data: No
- Informed consent:

6. Other issues

Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?

No